

LEADERSHIP ATTRIBUTES OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS AT OMAR DISTRICT MINISTRY OF BASIC HIGHER AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION IN SULU: TEACHER'S PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the Leadership Attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district on Academic year 2023-2024. It employed descriptive design with 100 teacher-respondents taken through purposive sampling method. The study found that: The teachers in Omar district were mostly young, female, and permanent. They agreed with the four leadership attributes and strongly agreed with the teaching planning. There were no differences in the perception of leadership attributes by demographic factors. There were low positive correlations between directive and supportive, and between supportive and teaching planning. The study suggests that: School administrators in Omar district should foster a positive and collaborative school culture by exhibiting leadership attributes such as vision, support, communication, and ethics; adapt their leadership styles and strategies to their teachers and students; and balance the gender representation and participation of the teaching staff. Teachers in Omar district should give feedback and suggestions to their administrators on their leadership attributes. The community in Omar, Sulu should support the school administrators and teachers in providing quality education for the students by engaging in the school activities and programs. Students should voice their opinions and needs to their school administrators and teachers, and join the school activities and programs. Researchers should explore further the leadership attributes of school administrators and their impact on the school culture and performance.

Keywords: *Leadership, leadership attributes, school administrators*

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is crucial in the 21st century. The success of any organization depends on the kind of leaders in managing at the helm of the institution. Leadership plays an indispensable role in effectiveness of an educational institution, right from the setting of goals to accomplishment of goals. Various researches have linked the school effectiveness with the leadership. In absence of leadership goal accomplishment and school effectiveness is never guaranteed.

Dr, sharma (2022) pointed out that Successful leadership is not the result of simply obtaining a position, but rather possessing the knowledge and understanding of successful leadership skills along with the personal ability to effectively implement those skills. Hence, "School leaders need impressive skills to provide effective leadership in our diverse school environments". However Leadership is not a concept for self but it should be rightly perceived by followers.

In view of Cheng and Townsend (2000) for education change and effectiveness, the role of principal is often crucial to their success. The principal is challenged to create the culture of quality that penetrates to the smallest elements, processes and the systems of an institution. It is common experience that under the same set of rules and regulations, with same set of teaching staff and students from similar background, an educational institution degenerates or maintains status quo, or rises to prominence with a change of principal. This is also borne out by large number of research studies on management of change in education, Mukhaopadhyay (2001).

However the functions of principal put a variety of demands and challenges for the principal Mestry and Grobler (2004). In an attempt to explain the requirements of a competent principal, Cranston (2002) explained the skills and capacities which principals are expected to possess.

Luo (2004) further contended that perceptions about principals as leaders by their teachers indicate an important dimension to evaluate the leaders capacities. According to him, understanding how teachers perceive their principals leadership capacities has a great significance and providing evidence for improvement of school leadership. Research has also demonstrated that teachers' perceptions of their principals' capabilities and their working conditions will determine the organizational climate and culture of the school. Such perceptions will also impact on the performance of the school.

A study by Luo and Najjar (2007), investigated Chinese principal leadership capacities as perceived by master teachers. Unlike in many developed countries where studies on principals' competencies are available in multitude, such studies are still at its low in Malaysia. Keeping in mind the importance of role of the principal as a leader within the secondary school system, it is imperative to examine the leadership attributes of school principals. This is particularly so because of the fact that schools in this country serve for the large section of national students. Most studies in this country have focused on leadership styles, rather than leadership attributes. The study therefore intends to fill

this gap by investigating the perception of teachers on the leadership attributes of their principals in terms of leadership capacities and leadership qualities.

In Omar district, the leadership attributes of administrators hold great significance from perspectives of teachers. These attributes not only shape the overall functioning of schools but also influence the experiences and outcomes of educators within the district. Effective administrators possess leadership qualities that inspire and empower teachers to excel in their roles, creating a conducive environment for teaching and learning.

Thus, this study aims to assess the leadership attributes of the administrators in Omar district.

Research Questions:

This study will determine the Leadership Attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district on Academic year 2023. Specifically, this research will gather information to answer each of the following questions.

1. What is the socio- demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Employment Status; and
 - 1.4 Length of Service?
- 2 What is the extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 Directives;
 - 2.2 Participative;
 - 2.3 Supportive;
 - 2.4 achievement oriented;
 - 2.5 Teaching planning;
 - 2.6 Monitoring and evaluation.
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of;
 - 3.1 Age;
 - 3.2 Gender;
 - 3.3 Employment Status; and
 - 3.4 Length of Service?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Research Design was used in research to refer to the researcher's plan of how to proceed. This design allows data to be collected at a single point in time and can be used for a descriptive study as well as determination of relationship between variable.

A descriptive research design method was employed in this study. Thus, this study will intent to describe, quantify, and infer as well as to discover relationships among variables which involves:

1. Demographic profile of teachers in terms of age, gender civil status, employment status, years in service.
2. Extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators in terms of Directives, Participative, supportive, achievement oriented, Teaching planning and Monitoring and evaluation.
3. The significant difference in the extent of Leadership style that promote administrators in terms of Directives, Participative, supportive, achievement oriented, Teaching planning and Monitoring and evaluation.
4. The significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the Leadership attributes that promote administrators in Omar district, Sulu.

The study was conducted among teachers in Omar district, Sulu. The respondents of this study is one hundred (100) selected teachers at Omar district, Sulu, were the main source of data which which was quantified to answer the research questions in this study. Library and internet were the source of information that will be used to enrich the theoretical and conceptual frameworks of this research, the data from the respondents will be collected through the use of questionnaires.

Research Locale

The study was conducted among teachers in Omar district School, Ministry of Basic Higher Technical Education (MBHTE), Sulu division during the Academic year 2023-2024.

Respondents of The Study

The respondents of the study were One hundred (100) respondents of which all are Teachers from different schools in Omar district under Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE), division- Sulu during the Academic year 2023-2024.

Selected teachers will be drawn to represent each of the school at Omar district, Division-Sulu. Table below shows the distribution of samples in this study.

Distribution of the Target Samples among Selected school.

Schools in Omar district	Number of Respondents
Sucuban Elementary School	10
Bandahala Elementary School	10
Angilan Elementary School	10
Kapual Elementary School	10
Imam Abdusali Elem. School	10
Andalan Elementary School	10
Huwit-Huwit Elementary School	10
Likubung Elementary School	10
Tanduh Panuan Elementary School	10
Kasulutan Elementary School	10
TOTAL	100

Sampling Design

In this study, the researcher used a purposive sampling, also known as judgmental selection or subjective sampling is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their surveys.

The researcher used purposively one hundred (100) respondents from Omar district. The use of purposive sampling study and help the study to meet its goals.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was the main instrument to be employed to gather data on the extent of leadership attributes of administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, Sulu during the Academic year 2023-2024.in the context of leadership attributes such as Directives, Participative, supportive, achievement oriented, Teaching planning and Monitoring and evaluation.

The questionnaire was adapted and patterned from the study of Allyn Vergabera

Jayoma, et al (2022) entitled reckoning of leadership styles and teacher's commitment And performance. This model encompasses the following attributes:

1. Directives,
2. Participative,
3. supportive,
4. Achievement oriented,
5. Teaching planning and

6. Monitoring and evaluation

The research instrument was utilized in this study consist of two parts. Part I of the questionnaire will focus on obtaining the demographic profile of the the respondents.

Part II focused towards obtaining data on the extent of Data to be obtained using this questionnaire will be analysed through 5-point modified Likert scale such as 5=Strongly Agree (SA), 4=Agree (A), 3=Uncertain (U), 2=Disagree (D), 1=Strongly Disagree (SD).

Data Gathering Procedure

The following procedure were employed in the course of data gathering: A permit to administer the questionnaire were sought from the office of the Dean of Graduates studies, Sulu state college through a formal letter and then a letter that addressed to the MBHTE, Division-Sulu unit head then, to the District Supervisor OF Omar District inorder to make them aware about the purpose of conducting the study. The launching and administering, as well as the retrieval of the questionnaire were conducted personally by the researcher. The researcher also ensures the confidentially and anonymity of responses to encourage honest answers.

Validity and Reliability

The instrument were used in this research will be adapted and patterned from The study of *Allyn Vergabera Jayoma, et al , (2022) entitled “reckoning of leadership Styles and teacher’s commitment and job performance.”*

It is a standardized research instrument with established validity and reliability. However, to suit its usability in the local setting, a slight modification will be made and this will be subjected to the perusal of at least two (2) experts from the faculty members of the School of Graduate Studies of Sulu state College.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistical tools wwere appropriately employed in the treatment of data to be gathered for this study, namely:

1. For research problem number one 1, which states: What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, employment status, length of service, the statistical tools to be used are frequency counts and percentage to determine the profile of the teachers.
2. For research problem number two 2, which states: What is the Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of, directives, participative, supportive, achievement oriented, teaching planning, monitoring and evaluation. The Statistical tools to be used are mean and standard deviation.

3. For research problem number three (3), which states: Is there a significant difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar District, MBHTE, division-Sulu?
4. For research problem number four (4), which states; what is the significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu? The statistical tools to be used is Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following are the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of results according to the research questions and the data analysis methods:

1. What is the socio- demographic profile of the respondents in terms of f 1.1 age, 1.2 gender, 1.3 employment status, and 1.4 length of service?

1.1 In terms of Age

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district under Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE), division- Sulu in terms of age. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, the majority is between 26-35 years old who make up 54% (54). This is followed by those aged 36-45 years, 25 years and below, and 46 years and above, accounting for 25% (25), 16% (16), and 5% (5) respectively. This means that the majority of the teacher-respondents are in their early adulthood stage. The table shows that there is a difference of at least 29% between the other groups. This implies a relatively skewed age distribution among the teacher-respondents.

Age	Number of Respondents	Percent
25 years old and below	16	16%
26-35 years old	54	54%
36-45 years old	25	25%
46 years old and above	5	5%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.1 Teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of age.

1.2 In terms of Gender

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district under Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE), division- Sulu in terms of gender. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, it highly concentrated toward females who make up 71% (71), while males account for 29% (29). This means that most of the teacher-respondents are female, and that there is a gender gap of 42% between female and male respondents. This implies a higher participation or representation of female teacher-respondents in the surveyed group.

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percent
Male	29	29%
Female	71	71%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.2 Teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of gender.

1.3 In terms of Employment Status

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district under Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE), division- Sulu in terms of employment status. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, the majority are permanent who make up 69% (69). This is followed by those with contract of service, and who are part-time, accounting for 20% (20, and 11% (11) respectively. This means that the majority of the teacher-respondents are permanent. The table shows that there is a difference of at least 49% between the other groups. This implies a relatively diverse range of employment status among the teacher-respondents, which is highly concentrated in the permanent group.

Employment Status	Number of Respondents	Percent
Permanent	69	69%
Contract of Service	20	20%
Part-time	11	11%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.3 Teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of employment status.

1.4 In terms of Length of Service

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district under Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE), division- Sulu in terms of length of service. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, majority have been employed for 6-10 years, making up 45% (45). This is followed by those who have been employed for 11-20 years, and 5 years and below, and 21 years and above, accounting for 27% (27), 20% (20), and 8% (8) respectively. This means that the majority of the teacher-respondents have less than a decade of experience as public teacher in Omar district, Sulu. The table shows that there is a difference of at least 18% between the other groups. This implies a slightly skewed length of service distribution among the teacher-respondents.

Length of Service	Number of Respondents	Percent
5 years and below	20	20%
6-10 years	45	45%
11-20 years	27	27%
21 years and above	8	8%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.4 Teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of length of service.

2. What is the extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of 2.1 Directives, 2.2 Participative, 2.3 Supportive, 2.4 Achievement oriented, and 2.5 Teaching planning?

2.1 In the context of Directives

Table 2.1 shows the extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of Directive. The result shows that the total mean score is 3.937, which indicates an overall rating of "Agree". The total standard deviation is 0.26915, which indicates that there is less variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents perceived the leadership attributes that promote administrators in terms of directives with high level.

The mean scores indicate that the teacher-respondents strongly agree that their principal let them know what is expected of him, informs them to follow standard rules and regulations, explains the level of performance that is expected of teachers. They also agree that their principal, but they strongly disagree that their principal gives vague explanations of what is expected of teachers on the job. The highest mean (4.88) is associated with the statement "The principal informs the teachers to follow standard rules and regulations," which means that teacher-respondents value clarity and guidance from their administrators. The lowest mean (1.46) is for "The principal gives vague explanations of what is expected of teachers on the job," which means that teacher-respondents do not appreciate ambiguity and confusion from their administrators.

Table 2.1 Extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of Directives.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. The principal let teachers know what is expected of him.	4.66	.517	Strongly Agree
2. The principal inform the teachers to follow standard rules and regulations.	4.88	.383	Strongly Agree
3. The principal explains the level of performance that is expected of teachers.	4.75	.687	Strongly Agree
4. The principal gives vague explanations of what is expected of teachers on the job.	1.46	1.058	Strongly Disagree
Total	3.9375	.26915	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.2 In the context of Participative

Table 2.2 shows the extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of Participative. The result shows that the total mean score is 3.9180, which indicates an overall rating of “Agree”. The total standard deviation is 0.44775, which indicates that there is less variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents perceived the leadership attributes that promote administrators in terms of participative with high level.

The mean scores indicate that the teacher-respondents agree that their principal consults with them when facing a problem, listens respectively to their ideas and suggestion, asks suggestion from them concerning how to carry-out assignments, and asks them for suggestion on what assignment should be made, but they are moderate that their act without consulting them. The highest mean (4.34) is associated with the statement “The principal listens respectively to teacher’s ideas and suggestion,” which means that teacher-respondents appreciate administrators who involve them in the decision-making process. The lowest mean (3.07) is for the statement “The principal act without consulting the teachers,” which means that teacher-respondents do not like administrators who exclude them from the decision-making process.

Table 2.2 Extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of participative.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. The principal Consults with teachers when facing a problem	4.19	.787	Agree
2. The principal Listens respectively to teacher’s ideas and suggestion.	4.34	.655	Agree
3. The principal Act without consulting the teachers	3.07	1.394	Moderate
4. The principal Asks suggestion from	3.90	.674	Agree

teachers concerning how to carry-out assignments.			
5. The principal asks the teachers for suggestion on what assignment should be made.	4.09	.570	Agree
Total	3.9180	.44775	Agree

Legend: **4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA)**, **3.50-4.49 = Agree (A)**, **2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M)**, **1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D)**, **1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)**

2.3 In the context of Supportive

Table 2.3 shows the extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of Participative. The result shows that the total mean score is 3.9480, which indicates an overall rating of “Agree”. The total standard deviation is 0.39453, which indicates that there is less variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents perceived the leadership attributes that promote administrators in terms of supportive with high level.

The mean scores indicate that the teacher-respondents strongly agree that their principal maintains a friendly working relationship with them and behaves in a manner that is thoughtful of their personal needs. They also agree that their principal does little things to make it pleasant to be a member of the group, and helps them overcome problems that stop them from carrying their task, but they disagree that their principal says things that hurts their personal feelings. The highest mean (4.63) is associated with the statement “The principal behaves in a manner that is thoughtful of teacher’s personal needs,” which means that teacher-respondents appreciate administrators who are considerate and respectful of their personal situations. The lowest mean (1.81) is for the statement “The principal says things that hurts teachers’ personal feelings,” which means that teacher-respondents do not tolerate administrators who are insensitive and rude.

Table 2.3 Extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of supportive.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. The principal maintains a friendly working relationship with teachers.	4.61	.634	Strongly Agree
2. The principal do little things to make it pleasant to be a member of the group.	4.26	1.011	Agree
3. The principal say things that hurts teachers personal feeling s.	1.81	1.398	Disagree
4. The principal helps teachers overcome problems that stop them from carrying their task.	4.43	1.057	Agree
5. The principal behaves in a manner that is thoughtful of teacher’s personal needs.	4.63	.614	Strongly Agree

Total	3.9480	.39453	Agree
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Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.4 In the context of Achievement Oriented

Table 2.4 shows the extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of achievement oriented. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.07, which indicates an overall rating of “Agree”. The total standard deviation is 0.32706, which indicates that there is less variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents perceived the leadership attributes that promote administrators in terms of achievement oriented with high level.

The mean scores indicate that the teacher-respondents agree that their principal let them know that they expect them to perform at their highest level, sets goals for their performance that are quiet challenging, encourages continual improvement in their performance, consistently sets challenging goals for them to attain, and shows no doubts about their ability to meet most objectives. The highest mean (4.19) is for the statement “The principal let teachers know that I expect them to perform at their highest level,” whihc means that teacher-respondents appreciate administrators who motivate and inspire them to achieve their full potential. The lowest mean (3.98) is for the statement “The principal shows no doubts about teacher’s ability to meet most objectives,” which means that teacher-respondents also value administrators who trust and respect their abilities.

Table 2.4 Extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of achievement oriented.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. The principal let teachers know that I expect them to perform at their highest level.	4.19	.465	Agree
2. The principal set goals for teacher performance that are quiet challenging	4.09	.379	Agree
3. The principal encourages continual improvement in teacher’s performance.	4.06	.397	Agree
4. The principal consistently set challenging goals for teachers to attain.	4.03	.413	Agree
5. The principal shows no doubts about teacher’s ability to meet most objectives.	3.98	.492	Agree
Total	4.0700	.32706	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.5 In the context of Teaching Planning

Table 2.5 shows the extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of teaching planning. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.8175, which indicates an overall rating of “Strongly Agree”. The total standard deviation is 0.41417, which indicates that there is less variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents perceived the leadership attributes that promote administrators in terms of teaching planning with very high level.

The mean scores indicate that the teacher-respondents strongly agree that their principal informs them to prepare well their lessons, informs them to teach at level of their learners’ competence and understanding, informs them to use the teaching media as well-planned, and help teachers plan effectively to engage learners in their classes. The highest mean (4.91) is for the statement “The principal helps teachers plan effectively to engage learners in their classes,” which means that teacher-respondents appreciate administrators who provide them with guidance, resources, and support to plan their lessons according to the curriculum and the students’ needs and interests. The lowest mean (4.68) is for the statement “The principal informs teachers to prepare well for their lessons,” which means that teacher-respondents also value administrators who remind them to be prepared and organized for their classes.

Table 2.5 Extent of Leadership attributes that promote administrators as perceived by teachers in terms of teaching planning.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. The principal informs teachers to prepare well their lessons	4.68	.618	Strongly Agree
2. The principal inform teachers to teach at level of their learners’ competence and understanding	4.80	.603	Strongly Agree
3. The principal inform teachers to use the teaching media as well-planned.	4.88	.456	Strongly Agree
4. The principal help teachers plan effectively to engage learners in their classes.	4.91	.351	Strongly Agree
Total	4.8175	.41417	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of 3.1 age, 3.2 gender, 3.3 employment status, and 3.4 length of service?

3.1 In terms of Age

Table 3.1 presents the difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of age. The variables include Directives, Participative, Supportive, Achievement oriented, and Teaching planning. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the perceptions of teacher-respondents aged 25 years and below on the extent of these variables do not differ from those aged 26-35 years, 36-45 years, and 46 years and above, or vice versa. This implies that the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu perceive the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators in the same way regardless of their age. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of age.” is accepted.

Table 3.1 Difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of age.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Directives	Between Groups	.227	3	.076	1.044	.377	Not Significant
	Within Groups	6.945	96	.072			
	Total	7.172	99				
Participative	Between Groups	.618	3	.206	1.028	.384	Not Significant
	Within Groups	19.230	96	.200			
	Total	19.848	99				
Supportive	Between Groups	1.036	3	.345	2.307	.081	Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.373	96	.150			
	Total	15.410	99				
Achievement Oriented	Between Groups	.126	3	.042	.384	.765	Not Significant
	Within Groups	10.464	96	.109			
	Total						

	Total	10.590	99				
Teaching Planning	Between Groups	.532	3	.177	1.035	.381	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.450	96	.171			
	Total	16.982	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.2 In terms of Gender

Table 3.2 presents the difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of gender. The variables include Directives, Participative, Supportive, Achievement oriented, and Teaching planning. The table shows that the mean difference and probability values for all variables are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the extent of these variables does not affect the perceptions of male and female teacher-respondents differently. This implies that the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu perceive the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators in the same way regardless of their gender. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of gender." is accepted.

Table 3.2 Difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of gender.

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
<i>Directives</i>	Male	3.9741	0.30869	.05160	0.869	0.387	Not Significant
	Female	3.9225	0.2521				
Participative	Male	3.9586	0.48808	0.05721	.578	.565	Not Significant
	Female	3.9014	0.43276				
Supportive	Male	4.0414	0.4049	.13152	1.523	.131	Not Significant
	Female	3.9099	0.38662				
Achievement oriented	Male	4.0552	0.30658	-0.02088	-.288	.774	Not Significant
	Female	4.0761	0.33699				
Teaching planning	Male	4.8966	0.2632	0.11134	1.223	0.224	Not Significant

	Female	4.785 2	0.4596 1				
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*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.3 In terms of Employment status

Table 3.3 presents the difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of employment status. The variables include Directives, Participative, Supportive, Achievement oriented, and Teaching planning. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the perceptions of teacher-respondents who are permanent on the extent of these variables do not differ from those of teacher-respondents who are part-time, and with contract of service, or vice versa. This implies that the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu perceive the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators in the same way regardless of their employment status. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of employment status." is accepted

Table 3.3 Difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division-Sulu in terms of employment status.

Sources of Variation		<i>Sum of Squares</i>	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
<i>Directives</i>	Between Groups	.124	2	.062	.850	.431	Not Significant
	Within Groups	7.048	97	.073			
	Total	7.172	99				
Participative	Between Groups	.260	2	.130	.644	.527	Not Significant
	Within Groups	19.587	97	.202			
	Total	19.848	99				
Supportive	Between Groups	.314	2	.157	1.010	.368	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.095	97	.156			
	Total	15.410	99				
Achievement Oriented	Between Groups	.176	2	.088	.820	.444	Not Significant
	Within	10.414	97	.107			

	Groups Total	10.590	99				
Teaching Planning	Between Groups	.587	2	.293	1.736	.182	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.395	97	.169			
	Total	16.982	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.4 In terms of Length of Service

Table 3.4 presents the difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of length of service. The variables include Directives, Participative, Supportive, Achievement oriented, and Teaching planning. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables, except for supportive aspect, are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the perceptions of teacher-respondents with under 5 years in service on the extent of these variables do not differ from those of teacher-respondents with 6-10 years, 11-20 years, and over 21 years in service, or vice versa. However, on the extent of supportive aspect, the teacher-respondents with under 5 years in service perceive differently than those with 11-20 years in service, or vice versa, as show in table 3.4.1. This implies that the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district, MBHTE, division-Sulu perceive the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators in the same way regardless of their length of service. However, there is a significant difference in their perceptions on the extent of supportive aspect among the groups. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of length of service." is accepted.

Table 3.4 Difference in the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu in terms of length of service.

Sources of Variation		<i>Sum of Squares</i>	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
<i>Directives</i>	Between Groups	.371	3	.124	1.747	.163	Not Significant
	Within Groups	6.801	96	.071			
	Total	7.172	99				
Participative	Between Groups	.875	3	.292	1.476	.226	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.973	96	.198			
	Total	19.848	99				
Supportive	Between	1.441	3	.480	3.301*	.024	Significant

	Groups						
	Within	13.969	96	.146			
	Groups						
	Total	15.410	99				
Achievement Oriented	Between	.447	3	.149	1.411	.244	Not Significant
	Groups						
	Within	10.143	96	.106			
	Groups						
	Total	10.590	99				
Teaching Planning	Between	.898	3	.299	1.787	.155	Not Significant
	Groups						
	Within	16.084	96	.168			
	Groups						
	Total	16.982	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test was conducted to identify which among groups classified according to length of service have different levels of mean in the extent of supportive aspect when data are grouped according to teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of length of service.

On Supportive aspect: It shows that teacher-respondents with under 5 years in service obtained the mean difference of $-.31852^*$ with the Standard Error of .11254 and p-value of .028 over teacher-respondents with 11-20 years in service which is significant at alpha 0.05.

Table 3.4.1 Multiple comparison of the extent of leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu by length of service.

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I – J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Supportive	5 years and below	6-10 years	-.09333	.10251	.799
		11-20 years	-.31852*	.11254	.028
		21 years and above	-.25000	.15957	.402

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu?

Table 4 presents the correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in

Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu. The table shows that the computed Pearson correlation Coefficients (Pearson r) between these categories, except between directives and supportive, and between supportive and teaching planning, are not significant at alpha 0.05. Based on the table, the following interpretation are as follows:

- 1) No linear correlations between directives and participative, achievement oriented, and teaching planning; low positive correlations between directives and supportive.
- 2) No linear correlations between participative and supportive, achievement oriented, and teaching planning.
- 3) No linear correlations between supportive and achievement oriented; low positive correlations between supportive and teaching planning.

This shows that sub-categories subsumed under the leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu are not strongly related. The result reveals that a low positive correlation between directives and supportive means that there is a weak relationship between the extent to which school administrators give clear and specific instructions to teachers and the extent to which they show concern and respect for teachers' needs and feelings. And a low positive correlation between supportive and teaching planning means that there is a weak relationship between the extent to which school administrators provide emotional and professional support to teachers and the extent to which they help teachers develop and implement effective teaching plans. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu." is accepted.

Table 4 Correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under leadership attributes of Elementary School Administrators as perceived by teachers in Omar district, MBHTE, division- Sulu.

Variables		Pearson r	Sig.	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
<i>Directives</i>	Participative	-.081	.425	100	
	Supportive	.197*	.049	100	Low
	Achievement Oriented	.085	.403	100	
	Teaching Planning	.146	.148	100	
Participative	Supportive	.127	.210	100	
	Achievement Oriented	.155	.122	100	
	Teaching Planning	.185	.065	100	
Supportive	Achievement Oriented	.151	.135	100	
	Teaching Planning	.244*	.014	100	Low

Achievement Oriented	Teaching Planning	.155	.124	100	
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*Correlation coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.3 = Low; 0.3-0.5 = Moderate; 0.5-0.7 = High; 0.7-0.9 = Very High; 0.9-1 = Nearly Perfect

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to data collection, participants will be provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, and confidentiality measures. Informed consent were obtained from all participants before their involvement in the research.

Participants' identities and sensitive information will be kept confidential throughout the study. Data will be securely stored and only accessed by the research ethics committee for analysis purposes.

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